

Kinetic studies on the oxidation of oxalate and malonate by bis(μ -oxo)manganese(III, IV)-cyclam complex[†]

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Kinetics and mechanism of the redox interaction of bis(μ -oxo)manganese(III,IV)-cyclam complex with oxalate and malonate in the range of pH 3.6-6.0 (acetate buffer) at 25° have been reported. Analysis of kinetic data reveals the formation of a hydrogen bonded adduct prior to the electron transfer. Both protonated and deprotonated forms of the manganese species take part in reaction revealed through pH-rate profiles.

Manganese in oxidation states higher than two is involved in redox processes at the active sites of several metalloproteins¹⁻³. The interest in biomimetic di(μ -oxo)dimanganese(III,IV) complexes originates in their potential use as redox catalysts^{4,5}. Among these the mixed valent bis(μ -oxo)manganese(III,IV) species with the core $[L_2Mn^{III}(O)_2Mn^{IV}L_2]^{3+}$ (L = bipyridine or *o*-phenanthroline) serve as good model compounds for the short Mn-Mn distances and multiple signal in the EPR spectrum of PS-II^{6,7}. Several polyazamacrocyclic complexes of manganese have been synthesized in order to demonstrate the mechanism of action of superoxide dismutases and photosystem-II (PS-II)⁸. Kinetic studies involving mixed-valent manganese complexes are reported in the literature, but to our knowledge, studies involving the $Mn^{III}(O)_2Mn^{IV}$ core with any macrocyclic ligand are scarce⁹. In the present investigation, we would like to report on the oxidation of two carboxylates, e.g. oxalate and malonate by $[L(Mn^{III}(O)_2Mn^{IV}L)]^{3+}$ (L=1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradecane) **1** over a wide range of pH. Studies on these carboxylates seem interesting in the sense that oxalate is used as a quencher in solar photochemistry and as a potential donor in the excited state of other electron transfer reactions^{10,11}.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry :

The stoichiometry for the oxidation of acids by **1** was determined spectrophotometrically at 650 nm. To a known excess of the complex was added variable concentration of the reductants in deficiency in presence of 0.02 mol dm⁻³ of acetate buffer. After the completion of the reaction (*ca.* 2.5 h) concentration of the unreacted complex was determined utilizing the known extinction coefficient of the complex at 650 nm ($\epsilon = 783 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in H₂O⁹. Parallel blank solutions of the complex without reductants under identical condition were also prepared to monitor the amount of the complex undergoing auto-decomposition. The final product corresponding to the complex was found to be Mn^{II} and was identified by EPR spectroscopy having a six-line spectrum at $g = 2.0$ region. The stoichiometric results indicate that 1.5 moles of the oxalate consume 1 mole of **1** whereas for malonate the ratio was found to be 0.70 : 1 expected for the malonate which behaves as a four-electron reductant with the formation of meso-oxalic acid as the oxidation product. The formation of the latter was confirmed by the reported method^{12,13}. Overall reactions with oxalate and malonate may be given as

Solution behavior of complex **1** :

Complex **1** is stable in aqueous medium for a reasonable time period but undergoes decomposition when kept for a prolonged time^{14,15}. However, in acetate buffer (pH 4.75–

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

6.0), the complex is stable enough (>2 h) and the kinetics can be followed conveniently. Rapid disappearance of the peaks at 653 and 551 nm. and appearance of a sharp peak at 265.5 and another at 358 nm were observed in the presence of $\text{HPO}_4^{2-} / \text{H}_2\text{PO}_4^-$ buffer with concomitant color change from deep green to greenish yellow⁹. Complex 1 exhibits a *d-d* transition band characteristics of Mn^{III} center having λ_{max} 550 nm ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 760 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)¹⁴. Additionally, the complex shows a broad band at 650 nm. In lower pH region, μ -oxo-bridged complexes such as 1 is reported to undergo protonation to yield (μ -oxo)(μ -hydroxo) species. More dominant feature at lower energy ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 740 \text{ nm}$) for the corresponding cyclen complex, an analog of 1, has been attributed to the formation of a (μ -oxo)(μ -hydroxo) species¹⁵. At $\text{pH} < 3.5$, the decomposition of the complex is rapid leading to the formation of mononuclear manganese(III) and manganese(IV) complexes^{16,17}. The acid decomposition process involves mono-protonation evident from the first order dependence of the decomposition rate on $[\text{H}^+]$

The cyclic voltammetry of the complex was previously carried out in acetonitrile^{14,15}. In dry acetonitrile 1 undergoes one electron reversible oxidation ($E_{1/2} = +0.65 \text{ V vs Ag/Ag}^+$) and one-electron reversible reduction ($E_{1/2} = -0.35 \text{ vs Ag/Ag}^+$). Due to the macrocyclic effect both oxidation and reduction waves are more reversible in comparison to its phen and bpy analogs. The one-electron oxidation and reduction products, $\text{Mn}^{\text{IV}}\text{-Mn}^{\text{IV}}$ and $\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}\text{-Mn}^{\text{III}}$, respectively, are stable enough and in the electrochemical time-scale both of them can be brought back almost quantitatively to the original mixed valence species by changing the electrolysis potentials. On addition of H_2O to the acetonitrile solution of 1, the peak current of the oxidation process increases substantially and difficulties have been encountered in carrying out cyclic voltammetry of complex 1 in aqueous medium. The UV/vis spectral pattern of the complex, however, did not change significantly in aqueous medium

Dependence on [oxalate] and [malonate] :

The time-dependent spectral scanning with the reductants shows continuous decrease of the absorbance of the complex in the range 300-800 nm. One representative spectral scan with malonate has been presented in Fig. 1. The kinetics for the oxidation of acids by 1 was followed under pseudo-first order condition keeping the reductant in large excess over the complex (≥ 10 times) and monitoring the decrease in absorbance of the oxidant at 550 nm. The observed rate constants ($k_{\text{obs}} / \text{s}^{-1}$) at constant hydrogen ion concentration and fixed ionic strength (conditions : $[\text{I}] = 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO_4), [buffer] = 0.02 mol dm^{-3} (acetate), wavelength = 550 nm and for oxalate $\text{pH} = 4.70$

Fig. 1. Spectral scanning for the oxidation of malonate by complex 1 at 25°; $[\text{I}] = 3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, [malonate] = 0.10 mol dm^{-3} , $\text{pH} = 4.60$, $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO_4) and 0.02 mol dm^{-3} acetate buffer in intervals of ca 3 min.

and for malonate $\text{pH} = 4.60$) for the oxidation of oxalate and malonate have been assembled in Table 1. Under this condition, plots of k_{obs} vs $[\text{Red}]_t$ (where $[\text{Red}]_t$ is either total concentration of oxalate or malonate) was found to display an ascending curve. Plot of k_{obs} vs $[\text{Red}]_t^2$, however, is a straight-line with negligible intercept on the rate axis and is consistent with the theoretical rate equation (3),

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 + k [\text{Red}]_t^2 \quad (3)$$

fitting of the observed data to the above equation leads to $k_0 = (6.82 \pm 1.0) \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k = (8.77 \pm 0.1) \times 10^{-1} \text{ dm}^6 \text{ mol}^{-2}$ for oxalate and $k_0 = (1.08 \pm 0.15) \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k = (4.58 \pm 0.009) \times 10^{-1} \text{ dm}^6 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for malonate.

Table 1. Pseudo-first order rate constants ($\pm 5\%$) for the oxidation of oxalate and melonate by complex 1 at 25°

$[\text{I}] = 1^{-3} \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO_4), [buffer] = 0.02 mol dm^{-3} (acetate), wavelength = 550 nm and for oxalate $\text{pH} = 4.70$ and for malonate 4.60

$10^2 [\text{ox}]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^3 k_{\text{obs}}$ s^{-1}	$10^2 [\text{mal}]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^3 k_{\text{obs}}$ s^{-1}
0.5	0.92	4.0	1.94
1.0	0.95	5.0	2.19
2.0	1.40	6.0	2.70
5.0	2.32	7.0	3.47
6.0	3.42	9.0	4.96
7.0	5.57	10	5.84
10	9.10	12	7.52
15	22.3	15	10.7
20	36.0	20	19.8

The k_0 values are comparable to each other in magnitude. It is due to the auto-decomposition of the complex in aqueous solution under the condition of kinetic study. We have further verified it by keeping 1 for a long time in aque-

ous medium^{14,17}. For the Cu²⁺ ion catalyzed oxidation of 2-mercaptosuccinic acid by **1** in aqueous medium, similar observation has been made, and the decomposition rate is independent of [H⁺] in the range of pH covered by the acetate buffer¹⁷.

Effect of pH :

The acidity dependence of the rate of the reactions was checked in the range of pH 3.6 – 6.0 at a fixed concentration of the reductants having *I* = 1.0 mol dm⁻³ and at 25°. The rate constants were found to increase with increase in [H⁺] and tend to saturation at higher concentration of the latter for both oxalate and malonate (Fig. 2). The reducing properties of the reductants are known to increase on deprotonation whereas reverse is true for the oxidants. In the range of pH studied the following protic equilibrium for oxalate and malonate are expected to exist :

The pK_{a1} values of both reductants are very low and in the range of pH studied the molecular form of the reductants will not exist. The increase in pH would increase the population of the deprotonated species of the reductants and consequently an increase in the rate of the reaction would

Fig. 2. Plot of *k*_{ox} (dm⁶ mol⁻² s⁻¹) vs [H⁺] (mol dm⁻³) for the oxidation of (O) oxalate and (■) malonate by complex **1** at 25°. Solid line represents the calculated values using eq. 13; conditions : [oxalate] = 0.15 mol dm⁻³, [malonate] 0.1 mol dm⁻³, [**1**] = 1–3 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, *I* = 1.0 mol dm⁻³ (NaClO₄), [buffer] = 0.02 mol dm⁻³ (acetate), wavelength = 550 nm.

have been expected. The pH-rate profile, however, is contrary to that expected from the thermodynamic potentials of the reductants. Complex **1** is coordinatively saturated and protic equilibrium involving aqua-hydroxo forms of the complex is not a suitable explanation for the observed acidity dependence. The μ-oxo-bridged complexes such as **1** are, however, known to undergo protonation in acidic solution involving one or both the μ-O oxygen¹⁵. The present oxidant is also susceptible to monoprotonation involving one of the oxo-bridges¹⁷. In the experimental range of pH, the acid-catalyzed decomposition rate of complex **1** was found to be negligibly small compared to the electron transfer rate. A protic equilibrium of the complex involving (μ-O)bridge seems to be the most reasonable explanation for the observed pH-dependency. We can consider two forms of **1** as kinetically active species. The monoprotonated species, Mn^{III}-Mn^{IV}H, is expected to be more reactive than [Mn^{III}-Mn^{IV}] from thermodynamic considerations. With increase in pH, population of the latter would prevail, and consequently fall in the rate constant values is apparent.

The following sequence may be proposed to accommodate the observed kinetics. The first step involves the association between the positively charged complex and the negatively charged reductants (Red⁻ and Red²⁻) to form relatively stable intermediate (denoted by IP) followed by the slow one-electron transfer path involving another molecule of the reductants leading to Mn^{III}-Mn^{III} species :

The generation of the radical was tested by the polymerization of acrylonitrile as usual. The subsequent steps involving the intermediate manganese, the reductant species and Red^\bullet are fast and, therefore, kinetically insignificant. One can frame a rate law (eq. 13) by consideration of the above sequence.

$$k_{\text{obs}} = [(k_1'K_c [\text{H}^+]^2 + k_2' [\text{H}^+]^3 + k_3'K_{a2}^2K_c + k_4'K_{a2}^2 [\text{H}^+]) / \{(K_a + [\text{H}^+])(K_c + [\text{H}^+])\}] [\text{Red}]_T^2 \quad (12)$$

$$k_{\text{ox}} = (k_1'K_c [\text{H}^+]^2 + k_2' [\text{H}^+]^3 + k_3'K_{a2}^2K_c + k_4'K_{a2}^2 [\text{H}^+]) / \{(K_a + [\text{H}^+])(K_c + [\text{H}^+])\} \quad (13)$$

where, $k_{\text{ox}} = k_{\text{obs}}/([a[\text{Red}]_T^2]$; $[\text{Red}]_T$ = total concentration of the oxalate or malonate; a , the stoichiometric factor = 3/2 for oxalate and 3/4 for malonate and $k' = kQ$.

Fitting of the observed data in the above equation (Fig. 2) leads to the following parameters.

For oxalate : $k_1' = (2.25 \pm 0.3) \text{ dm}^6 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_2' = (3.07 \pm 0.10) \text{ dm}^6 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_3' = (3.94 \pm 1.2) \times 10^{-2} \text{ dm}^6 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_4' = (0.57 \pm 0.13) \text{ dm}^6 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $K_a = (2.66 \pm 0.16) \times 10^{-5}$, $K_c = (1.99 \pm 0.9) \times 10^{-5}$.

For malonate $k_1' = (3.38 \pm 0.9) \times 10^{-1} \text{ dm}^6 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; $k_2' = (1.67 \pm 0.18) \text{ dm}^6 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; $k_3' = (5.23 \pm 1.2) \times 10^{-2} \text{ dm}^6 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; $k_4' = (2.53 \pm 1.1) \text{ dm}^6 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; $K_{a2} = (6.10 \pm 2.0) \times 10^{-6}$; $K_c = (1.43 \pm 0.37) \times 10^{-4}$.

The kinetically determined $\text{p}K$ values of oxalate and malonate are comparable to those observed previously. The K_c values are also in agreement with that observed previously for the present oxidant showing the validity of the above mechanistic paths¹⁷.

Mechanistic conclusions :

Oxo-bridged mixed valence manganese(III,IV) complexes are recognized to be the most important model complexes for the oxygen evolving complex (OEC) in PS-II. Being coordinatively saturated, complex **1** is expected to undergo outer-sphere electron transfer reaction with simple reducing agents, and this is exemplified by the oxidation of hydroquinone in aqueous BES buffer⁹. The present study, however, indicates an association of the oxidant with the reductants to form relatively stable intermediates prior to electron transfer act. The apparent contrast is due to the presence of acidic proton on the reductants which is susceptible to undergo hydrogen bonded adduct formation. Apart from this, the electrostatic attraction between the positively charged oxidant (+3 for **1**) and negatively charged reductants (Red^- and Red^{2-} available in the present pH

range) should lead to the formation of outer-sphere ion-pairs supported by hydrogen bonding. The observed pH-dependency is interesting owing to the operation of two opposing effects. Lowering of pH would increase the population of $\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}\text{-Mn}^{\text{IV}}\text{H}$ with higher reactivity than its deprotonated form $\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}\text{-Mn}^{\text{IV}}$ causing an enhancement of rate. On the other hand, formation of protonated forms (red^-) of the reductants having lower reactivity than the deprotonated ones (red^{2-}) is favored on lowering the pH, and that would impart an opposite effect of slowing down the rates. It may be noted that the higher reactivity of the protonated forms of the reductants is observed over the deprotonated ones when the electron transfer reactions proceed through initial hydrogen bonding association between the reactants¹⁸. The kinetic evidences gathered in the present study indicate that an electrostatic adduct formation precedes the electron transfer step. This discards the possibility of an outer-sphere mechanism expected from the structural features of **1** which does not possess any vacant site to bind with.

Experimental

The complex di- μ -oxo-bis(1,4,8,11-tetraaza-cyclotetradecane)dimanganese(III,IV) perchlorate, $[\text{Mn}_2^{\text{III/IV}}(\mu\text{-O})_2(\text{cyclam})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_3$, abbreviated as $[\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}\text{-Mn}^{\text{IV}}]$ was synthesized according to the literature procedure^{14,15} and was characterized by elemental analysis and UV/v is spectroscopy : λ_{max} , nm (ϵ_{max} , $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in water 650(783), 550(760), 375(2432)⁹. The carboxylic acids were of reagent grade and used without further purification. Ionic strength of the solutions was adjusted with recrystallized sodium perchlorate (Aldrich, A.R.).

Physical measurements and kinetics :

The analytical purity of the complex was ascertained through microanalysis (CHN) in a Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer. pH was measured with a Systronics 335 pH meter. pH of the solutions was held constant with dilute perchloric acid / NaOH utilizing acetate buffer in the measured range of kinetic study. The electrodes were calibrated by standard aqueous buffers available commercially. The observed pH was corrected by using the relationship, $\text{p}[\text{H}^+] = -\log[\text{H}^+] = \text{pH} - A$, where $A = 0.1 \pm 0.02$ (calibration factor). Ionic strength was maintained at 1.0 mol dm^{-3} (NaClO_4) and the total ionic strength was calculated from the contribution of all the ionic species present in the medium at a particular pH. The spectral and kinetic studies were performed in an Shimadzu UV-2100 spectrophotometer equipped with thermostated cell compartments. The kinetics was followed at the λ_{max} of the complex (550 nm.) The absorbance-time plots showed single exponential de-

curves for the oxidation of both oxalate and malonate. The curves were analyzed by using non-linear computer-fit program.

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